

**MEANS OF EXPRESSING CATEGORY OF NEGATION IN CONTEMPORARY
ENGLISH: EXAMPLES AND SCIENTIFIC VIEWS****Dildora Buranova**

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Abstract. *The article deals with ways of expressing negation in modern English and the features of its expression. We gave the definition of negation from the point of view of various scientists. In addition, we analyze the ways of expressing negation in the texts of English-language fiction. Currently, in the English language there are a fairly large number of ways to express negation: negative particles, negative pronouns, double negation, antonyms, etc. In this regard, for persons studying English as a foreign language, the urgent question is what form of expression suitable for a specific situation.*

Keywords: *indicator of negativity, category of negation (predicative and non-predicative), partial and general negation, locative.*

**СПОСОБЫ ВЫРАЖЕНИЯ КАТЕГОРИИ ОТРИЦАНИЯ В СОВРЕМЕННОМ
АНГЛИЙСКОМ ЯЗЫКЕ: ПРИМЕРЫ И НАУЧНЫЕ ВЗГЛЯДЫ**

Аннотация. *В статье рассматриваются способы выражения отрицания в современном английском языке и особенности его выражения. Мы дали определение отрицания с точки зрения различных ученых. Кроме того, анализируются способы выражения отрицания в текстах англоязычной художественной литературы. В настоящее время в английском языке существует достаточно большое количество способов выражения отрицания: отрицательные частицы, отрицательные местоимения, двойное отрицание, антонимы и т. д. В связи с этим для лиц, изучающих английский язык как иностранный, актуален вопрос, какая форма выражения, подходящего для конкретной ситуации.*

Ключевые слова: *показатель отрицательности, категория отрицания (предикативное и непредикативное), частичное и общее отрицание, местный падеж.*

INTRODUCTION

Since ancient times, negation has been one of those linguistic categories that existed in every language. Therefore, it is difficult to fully understand the basis of linguistic negation if one does not study the history of the development of this category, the history of the ways in which it is expressed.

Negation is inherent in all languages of the world of initial, semantically indecomposable semantic categories that cannot be defined with the help of simpler semantic elements. The special position of the category of negation in comparison with other categories is emphasized by such representatives of linguistic schools as A.M. Peshkovsky, V.V. Vinogradov, F. Palmer.

RESEARCH METHOD AND METHODOLOGY

Well-known domestic linguist A.M. Peshkovsky pointed out that “the essence of this category, which has a colossal logical and, mainly, psychological significance (after all, negation and affirmation mutually determine each other), and where there is no affirmation, there is no truth, there is no human thought” [1: 386].

According to such linguists as O. Jespersen and Russian scientist A. A. Potebnya, negation is a purely subjective manifestation of the human psyche. Negation is interpreted as the generation of various mental (sensual) reactions of the speaker, as an expression of a feeling of prohibition, resistance, a contradiction between the actual and the expected (or even possible), as a reflection of a feeling of contrast, disgust, a feeling of disappointment, etc. Thus, according to this approach, denial is a manifestation of the human psyche, his emotional and psychological feelings, and not a reflection of reality [2: 27].

Accordingly, negation is an element of the meaning of the sentence, which indicates the connections that are established between the components of the sentence. From the speaker's point of view, negation indicates that there is no reality, or that the corresponding affirmative sentence is rejected by the speaker as erroneous. Most often, a negative statement occurs when the corresponding affirmative statement has been made before or is included in the general presumption of the speakers.

In modern English, the concept of negation can be expressed using prefixes, suffixes, particles and negative pronouns: a) one of the main ways of expressing negation is affixation, "Scientific interdisciplinary research" a way of forming words with the help of affixes. In the word-formation processes of the English language, affixation, which is represented by prefixation and suffixation, occupies a special place. A number of affixes presented below can form new words from different parts of speech and not form new parts of speech. Words formed by prefixation remain the same part of speech from which they are formed. For example: clear - unclear, rest - restless, equal - unequal, comfortable - uncomfortable, advice - misadvice, use - useless, believe - misbelieve, advantage - disadvantage, approve - disapprove, honest - dishonest, weight - underweight, visible - invisible, relevant - irrelevant, moral - immoral.

No one is useless in this world who lightens the burdens of another (Ch. Dickens, 123)

A bit of a scare shot through Tom - a touch of discomfort suspicion (Ch. Dickens, 57)

As we can see, in the above sentences, negation is expressed by different parts of speech.

b) the most productive way of expressing negation is the 'not' particle, which is an auxiliary invariable word in English used to clarify, strengthen, limit or negate other words or phrases in a sentence, as well as convey modal and expressive meanings. They serve to form a semantic connection or grammatical form of a word, belong to the service parts of speech. The particle not most often refers to the predicate and through it to the entire content of the entire sentence, for example:

Not exactly relishing this, I said, "Never mind me, Joe." (Ch. Dickens, 241).

Not to mention bearers, all the money that could be spared were wanted for my mother (Ch. Dickens, 163).

RESEARCH RESULTS

The particle "not", as we see in the above sentences, can also be a separate word expressing negation.

c) the expression of negativity in a lexical way, i.e., negative pronouns and negative adverbs that indicate the absence

XVI International scientific-practical conference of the subject or feature. They are correlative, on the one hand, with indefinite pronouns, on the other hand, with generalizing ones, denying the

existence of the concept that the mentioned pronouns express: “no”, “neither”, “no one”, “nothing”, “none”, “nowhere”, for example:

The strange man looked at nobody but me (Ch. Dickens, 57).

I could see nothing else but black darkness (Ch. Dickens, 241).

A few faces hurried to glowing windows and looked after us, but none came out (Ch. Dickens, 94).

Thus, we see that in these sentences, the main way of expressing negation is negative pronouns (nobody, nothing, none).

During the analysis, it was found that one of the ways to express negation is abbreviated negation (abbreviated negation), which involves the use of short forms, where it is quite acceptable, mainly in colloquial speech:

I amn't happy - I'm not happy (Ch. Dickens, 84).

Another way is transferred negation. The transfer of negation is carried out in subordinate clauses with the union that. In such sentences, the particle not, provided that it is located after such verbs as believe, suppose, think, is transferred to the main sentence:

I don't think that need be considered = I think we needn't be considered (Ch. Dickens, 121).

As we can see, in the first part of the sentence, the negative particle comes before the auxiliary verb, since there is a conjunction that, and in the second part, the particle comes after the auxiliary verb.

Morphological means of expressing negation

The morphological features of a part of speech are considered by LS Barkhudarov as "a system of inflectional morphemes that characterize this part of speech, that is, grammatical categories inherent in this group of words." The morphological ways of expressing negation include affixation, represented by prefix and suffix. They occupy a special position in the word-formation processes taking place in the English language. First of all, they, as a rule, do not form new parts of speech, the same prefix can, and form new words from different parts of speech. The newly formed words remain the same part of speech from which they are formed, for example: common(usual)-uncommon(unusual), grateful-ungrateful satisfactory -unsatisfactory, trained - untrained, ability - disability, approval - disapproval, trust -distrust, responsible – irresponsible.

DISCUSSION

The most extensive group of prefixes in English is negative prefixes. Let's consider them in more detail. The un- prefix occurs in various forms in many Indo-European languages. In modern English, it has survived in the form in which it was used in Old English. This is a very productive prefix and easily forms new words from different parts of speech: ungrateful, unwritten (unwritten), unemployment, inhumanly. Most often, this prefix is found in adjectives and adverbs, for example: The only thing that makes me unhappy is that I'm making you unhappy (Graham 1976: 49).

As with the negative particle not-, words with the prefix un- express not just negation, but a new quality, a new sign: wise - means "wise; wise", and unwise has a different meaning (unreasonable) and approaches the meaning of foolish (stupid; foolish; reckless). The word unhappy rather means miserable (poor, poor). Usually, antonyms from adjectives with un- are

not formed using un-, but using the suffix less-for example: careful - careless hopeful - hopeless (unhopeful), thoughtful - thoughtless.

The barometer is useless: it is as misleading as the newspaper forecast. (Richard 1984: 70).

- *The barometer is useless: it is as deceptive as the forecast in the newspaper.*

The Latin prefix in-, akin to the Germanic prefix un-, appeared in loanwords from the French language: Incorrect, indifferent, innumerable, inactive

The in- prefix has the options il-, im-, ir-; il- in words starting with l-, im- in words starting with p-, b-, m-, and ir- in words starting with r-, for example: Illegal, illiterate, immotile, irresponsible, impossible.

The prefix mis- is of common Germanic origin. It most often forms derivatives from verb stems, for example: mistrust, miscalculate, misfit, misguide

Some words have words of negativity, while others have "wrong" expressions of action: miscalculate - miscalculate ("wrong"), mistrust - not to trust ("negativity").

The prefix dis- Latin origin, appeared in English in the Middle English period as part of borrowed French words: disarm, discover, disdain, disfigure, disguise. Like most derivational elements of non-native English origin, the dis- prefix as a means of forming English words began to be used both with bases of French origin and with English bases. This prefix forms derivatives from the stems of nouns, verbs, adjectives:

- *When critics disagree the artist is in accord with himself (Wild 1979: 19).*

The meaning of this prefix, or rather the meaning obtained by a derived word with this prefix, is the negation of the quality, feature, or action expressed by the stem of the derived word.

The anti- prefix is of Greek origin, it is larger than the listed prefixes and retains its lexical meaning - 'against'. This prefix appeared only in the New England period, its use is limited to the literary-book style of speech. Most often it is found in words expressing socio-political and scientific concepts: antifascist, anticyclone, anticlimax, and antithesis. Some independence of the meaning of this prefix is also reflected in the graphic design of the derivative word, many such derivatives are written with a hyphen: anti-social, anti-aircraft, anti-Jacobin etc. So, we can draw the following conclusions: in the presence of negative suffixes and prefixes, the vast majority of negative affixes are prefixes. Many researchers note that the compatibility of negative affixes with the stems of various parts of speech varies both from language to language, and within the same language.

When names of adjectives and (less often) nouns, the prefixes un- (homonym to the verb un-), non-, in- (im-, il-, ir-, dis-, mis- are most often used. The prefixes un-, pop-, in-, as evidenced by the existence of doublet words that differ little from each other in their meanings: nonprofessional - unprofessional non-professional, non-acceptable - unacceptable.

Thus, negative affixes in English are attached only to noun stems. Verb stems are not combined with negative affixes, because verbal negation is transmitted in this language by the analytical form of the verb with the particle not.

CONCLUSION

Thus, our analysis showed that negation is studied in English from different points of view. In addition, negation takes various forms, is expressed by various parts of speech and can be subject, predicate, object, circumstance. Also, the meaning of negation can be transmitted not only with the help of prefixes, but also "Scientific interdisciplinary research" of negative verbs,

nouns, adverbs, pronouns. Apart from this, it was found that certain characteristics of negative sentences are formed not only with the particle “not”, but also with other units of negation, that is, sentences with a touch of negation are formed the cumulative effect of all negative units.

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